

Fuzzy Range Labeling of Fuzzyhelm and Bistar Graphs

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Abstract

The main objective of this paper is to introduce fuzzy range labeling and look at this for some graph families subject to suitable conditions. In this article, the authors have introduced a new idea in fuzzy graph labeling called fuzzy range labeling. A graph G that can be assigned values as the difference between the maximum and minimum values in fuzzy graph labeling strategy and if all the vertex and edge values are distinct, is called fuzzy graph labeling. If G admits fuzzy range labeling then G is called fuzzy range graph. The authors have explored fuzzy range labeling on Helm graph, Bistar graph, star friendship graph.

Keywords: *Helm graph, Bistar graph, star friendship graph., Fuzzy Range Labeling, Range Labeling.*

Introduction

Graph Labeling concept was first introduced by Ros in 1967. It is one of the most interesting topics in Graph Theory (1). Range Labeling was first introduced and developed by R. Jahir Hussain and J. Senthamizh Selvan (2) who applied this notation to some graphs.

Due to the natural existence of uncertainty, Fuzzy Graph definition was first introduced by Kaufmann (1973) based on Zadeh's (3) fuzzy relations (1965). In 1975, Azriel Rosenfeld developed the Fuzzy Graph Theory independently. A fuzzy graph is based on the crisp graph. Hence, it is normal that numerous characteristics are comparable to crisp graph while yet varying in several places. Fuzzy Labeling Graphs has been introduced and studied by A. Nagoor Gani and D. Rajalaxmi (4) who discussed about the properties of fuzzy labeling graphs. A research on fuzzy labeling has tremendous growth in recent days especially remarkable progress have happened in 20th century. Fuzzy labeling has so many applications in various fields of Mathematics and Engineering especially in Science and Technology. Information Theory, Neural Networks, Cluster Analysis, Medical Diagnosis, Control Theory, etc. In addition do that, the paper is the further contribution on fuzzy graph labeling." Fuzzy Range Labeling of Helm Graph and Bistar Graph."

Preliminries

Definition 2.1: FUZZY LABELING GRAPH

The bijective functions $\sigma : V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu : V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ subject to the conditions $\mu(u, v) < \sigma(u)$ for all $u, v \in V$, is called fuzzy labeling. A graph which admits fuzzy labeling is called fuzzy labeling graph.

Definition 2.2: Range Labeling

Let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph with n vertices. A bijection on $f: V \rightarrow \{1,2,3,\dots,n\}$ is called a Range Labeling if for each edge E is distinct and E is defined by $f^*(E)=\text{Maximum Value}(v_k, v_{k+1}) - \text{Minimum Value}(v_k, v_{k+1})$. If a graph G admits range labeling, We say G is a range graph.

Definition 2.3: Fuzzy Range Labeling

If fuzzy labeling exists along with range labeling condition, in which all the vertex or edge or both values are distinct, we say it is called Fuzzy Range Labeling. A fuzzy graph which admits fuzzy range labeling is called a Fuzzy Range Graph.

Definition 2.4: HelmGraph

The helmgraph H_n is the graph obtained from an n -wheel graph by adjoining a pendent edge to each vertex of the cycle.

Definition 2.5: Bistar Graph

The Bistargraph $\overline{B_{m,n}}$ is the graph obtained from K_2 by joining m pendent edges to one end and n pendent edges to the other end of K_2 .

Results

Theorem 3.1

For $n \geq 3$, the Helm graph H_4 is a fuzzy Range labeling.

Proof:

In H_4 , when Y is to be assigned values from 0.2 to 1 i.e., $0.2 \leq y \leq 1$, all the edge values in the outer cycle are multiples of 2 and the graph is fuzzy range labeling helm graph.

Let the helm graph H_4 's centre vertex, other vertices in the outer cycle and the pendent vertices be $y, u_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ and $v_i (i = 5, 6, 7, 8)$ respectively.

In this cycle, Let $\alpha(y) = 0.2$ and $\beta(y, a_i) = 0.01$
 $\beta(u_i, u_{i+1}) = i \times 0.02$ and
 $\beta(v_i, u_i) = i \times 0.02$, where $v_i (i = 5, 6, 7, 8)$ and $u_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$.

Illustration:3.1.1

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(u_1, u_2) &= 1 \times 0.02 = 0.02 & \beta(v_5, u_1) &= 5 \times 0.02 = 0.10 \\ \beta(u_2, u_3) &= 2 \times 0.02 = 0.04 & \beta(v_6, u_2) &= 6 \times 0.02 = 0.12 \\ \beta(u_3, u_4) &= 3 \times 0.02 = 0.06 & \beta(v_7, u_3) &= 7 \times 0.02 = 0.14 \\ \beta(u_4, u_1) &= 4 \times 0.02 = 0.08 & \beta(v_8, u_4) &= 8 \times 0.02 = 0.16 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, all the edge and vertex values are distinct and the edges are multiples of 2.

A Helm graph is a Fuzzy Helm graph $(\overline{H_n})$ consists of two vertex sets U and V with $|U| > 1$ and $|V|=1$ such that $\mu(v, u_i) > 0$ $\mu(u_i, u_{n+1}) > 0$ and $\mu(u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}) = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

If the fuzzy Helm graph is range labeling, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(u_i, u_{i+1}) &= i \times 0.02 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n \\ \mu(u_i, u_{n+1}) &= (n + 1) \times 0.02 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n. \\ \mu(v, u_{i+1}) &= \mu(u_i, u_{i+1}) + \mu(v, u_i) \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.1.2

Consider the fuzzy Helm graph $(\overline{H_4})$. Here $n=4$
 When $\sigma(v)$ starts from 10
 Here, $\sigma : v \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\sigma : u_i \rightarrow [0,1]$

Figure (1) Fuzzy Helm graph $(\overline{H_4})$

In this figure, for the outer cycle,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(u_1, u_2) &= 1 \times 0.02 = 0.02 \\ \mu(u_2, u_3) &= 2 \times 0.02 = 0.04 \\ \mu(u_3, u_4) &= 3 \times 0.02 = 0.06 \\ \mu(u_4, u_1) &= 4 \times 0.02 = 0.08 \end{aligned}$$

For the pendent vertices,

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(u_1, u_5) &= 5 \times 0.02 = 0.10 \\ \mu(u_2, u_6) &= 6 \times 0.02 = 0.12 \\ \mu(u_3, u_7) &= 7 \times 0.02 = 0.14 \\ \mu(u_4, u_8) &= 8 \times 0.02 = 0.16\end{aligned}$$

Also, Let us take

$$\mu(v, u_1) = 0.01 \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(v, u_2) &= 0.03 = \mu(v, u_1) + \mu(u_1, u_2) \\ \mu(v, u_3) &= 0.07 = \mu(v, u_2) + \mu(u_2, u_3) \\ \mu(v, u_4) &= 0.13 = \mu(v, u_3) + \mu(u_3, u_4)\end{aligned}$$

By using the above membership functions, we have defined the membership values of the vertices.

For the outer cycle,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(u_1) &= 0.29 = \sigma(v) - \mu(v, u_1) \\ \sigma(u_2) &= 0.27 = \sigma(v) - \mu(v, u_2) \\ \sigma(u_3) &= 0.23 = \sigma(v) - \mu(v, u_3) \\ \sigma(u_4) &= 0.17 = \sigma(v) - \mu(v, u_4)\end{aligned}$$

For the pendent vertices,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(u_5) &= 0.19 = \sigma(u_1) - \mu(u_1, u_5) \\ \sigma(u_6) &= 0.15 = \sigma(u_2) - \mu(u_2, u_6) \\ \sigma(u_7) &= 0.09 = \sigma(u_3) - \mu(u_3, u_7) \\ \sigma(u_8) &= 0.01 = \sigma(u_4) - \mu(u_4, u_8)\end{aligned}$$

Since all the membership values of the edges are greater than zero and $\mu(u, v) \leq \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)$

In the similar way, for any value of $\sigma: v \rightarrow [0,1]$, the labeling of all vertices in the outer cycle and the pendent vertices u_i are distinct when $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Therefore, this Helm graph admits fuzzy Range labeling.

Theorem 3.2

All fuzzy Bistar graph $\widetilde{B}_{m,n}$ admits fuzzy Range labeling.

Proof:

Let $\widetilde{B}_{m,n}$ be a fuzzy Bistar graph consists of the vertex sets $\{u, v, u_i, v_j / 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ with $|u_i| > 1, |v_j| > 1$ where u_i and v_j are the pendent vertices such that $\mu(v, u) > 0$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(v, u_m) &> 0, \mu(v, v_n) > 0 \text{ and} \\ \mu(u_r, u_{r+1}) &= 0 \text{ for } 1 \leq r \leq m\end{aligned}$$

$$\mu(v_j, v_{j+1}) = 0 \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n$$

Let $\sigma(v), [0,1]$ and $\sigma(u), [0,1]$ then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(u, u_i) &= \frac{i}{100} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m \\ \mu(v, v_j) &= \frac{j}{100} \text{ for } i = m+1, m=2, \dots \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq m \\ \sigma(u_i) &= \sigma(u) - \mu(u, u_i) \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m \\ \sigma(v_j) &= \sigma(v) - \mu(v, v_j) \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n \\ \mu(uv) &= |\sigma(u) - \sigma(v)|\end{aligned}$$

If the number of pendent vertices is $m+n$ then the number of edges is $m+n+1$.

If the number of pendent vertices is $m+n$ then $\sigma(u)$ starts from $(m+n+1)/100$ and $\sigma(v)$ starts from $2(m+n+1)/100$

Example 3.2.1

Fuzzy Range labeling of fuzzy Bistar graph $\widetilde{B}_{4,5}$

Figure (2) Fuzzy Bistar graph $\widetilde{B}_{4,5}$ ($m < n$)

In this figure, $m=4, n=5$ In this case $m+n=9$.

Therefore $\sigma(u)$ starts from $1/10$ and $\sigma(v)$ starts from $2/10$ $\mu(u, u_1) = 1/100 = 0.01$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(u, u_2) &= 0.02, \mu(u, u_3) = 0.03, \mu(u, u_4) = 0.04 \\ \mu(v, v_1) &= 5/100 = 0.05 \\ \mu(v, v_2) &= 0.06, \mu(v, v_3) = 0.07, \mu(v, v_4) = 0.08\end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\sigma(u_1) = \sigma(u) - \mu(u, u_1) = \frac{1}{10} - 0.01 = 0.09 \text{ Similarly}$$

$$\sigma(u_2) = 0.08, \sigma(u_3) = 0.07, \sigma(u_4) = 0.06$$

$$\sigma(v_1) = \sigma(v) - \mu(v, v_1) = \frac{2}{10} - 0.05 = 0.15$$

$$\sigma(v_2) = 0.14, \sigma(v_3) = 0.13,$$

$$\sigma(v_4) = 0.12, \sigma(v_5) = 0.11$$

$$\text{and } \mu(uv) = |\sigma(u) - \sigma(v)| = 0.10$$

Since the membership functions of edges are all distinct in $\mu(u, u_i)$ and $\mu(v, v_j)$ as well as $\mu(u, u_i) < \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(u_i)$, $i = 1$ to m and $\mu(v, v_j) < \sigma(v) \wedge \sigma(v_j)$, $j = 1$ to n

Since all the membership values of the vertices are distinct, this Bistar graph admits fuzzy Range labeling.

Illustration 3.2.2

Fuzzy Range labeling of fuzzy Bistar graph $\overline{B_{4,5}}$

Conclusion

The new idea called Fuzzy Range Labeling has been introduced and analysed to Helm graph, Bistar graph in this article. Also, we have proved those graphs are Fuzzy Range Labeling. We invented to continue this research work on a few more graphs.

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